

A Study on Evaluation of Handloom Weavers' Training Programmes Provided in Thoppampatti Block of Dindigul District in Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The training programme for handloom weavers needs for modernization of handloom technology and skill up gradation for weaving process. The hand loom weavers need for training on loom setting, pre loom activities, weaving, Dyeing, Frequent design changing, introducing new variety, Repairing and replacing the damaged loom accessories and weaving defect free cloths. In addition to it, development and awareness programmes are needed for the modern marketing practices, costing and co-operative management. The both state and central governments are taking the accountability to impart the training to poor hand loom artisans. The handloom training centers are established in Erode, Paramagudi, Kumpakonum, and Kanchipuram as a specialized institute to provide the various types of training programmes for the weavers in the respective handloom circles in Tamil nadu. In additions to it, weavers services centers (WSCs) are taking the responsibility of conducting the training for handloom weavers in all the district of Tamil nadu

Introduction

The handloom textiles sector is considered as a heritage and culture of India. The span of history of the hand loom sector has been perceived as from the Vedic Era to present Knowledge Era. The Indian Share of global production of Handloom Goods has been estimated as 90 percent. Nearly 43.31 lakh weaving and allied workers who are belonging to below poverty line are generating the employment opportunities with producing the handmade fiber in 23.77 lakh handlooms for live hood from this unorganized scatted hand loom industry. The institutionalization of scatted handloom sector has been done by the head Development Commissioner of Hand loom sector after the independence of India. The average annual production of handloom sector is recorded as 6900 million Square Meters. The handloom weavers' co-operative societies (WCSs) and Master weavers (MWs) are the entrepreneurs of this sector. In addition to it,

the state government are also play the role of entrepreneurship to promote the economically weaker handloom community. For this purpose both the central and state governments are implanting the development scheme such as rebate subsidiary, interest subsidiary, transport subsidiary and marketing assistances schemes to WCSs and welfare schemes such as health insurance scheme, pension schemes, work shed, weavers housing scheme through the India. In this connection, the various Training programmes are offering to handloom artisans for the technology up gradation skill development and value addition of handloom products.

Training programme for Hand Weavers

Training intends to develop specific and useful knowledge, skill and techniques. Training is basically a task oriented activity which prepares peoples to carry out predetermined tasks. Development is a complex process wherein the individuals learn, grow, improve their abilities to perform a wide variety of roles within and outside the organization and acquire desirable attitudes and values. Thus development includes training to increase skill in performing a job as well as education to increase general knowledge and understanding of business circumstances. The training programme for handloom weavers needs for modernization of handloom technology and skill up gradation for weaving process. The hand loom weavers need for training on loom setting, pre loom activities, weaving, Dyeing , Frequent design changing, introducing new variety, Repairing and replacing the damaged loom accessories and weaving defect free cloths. In addition to it, development and awareness programmes are needed for the modern marketing practices, costing and co-operative management. The both state and central governments are taking the accountability to impart the training to poor hand loom artisans. The handloom training centers are established in Erode, Paramagudi, Kumpakonum, and Kanchipuram as a specialized institute to provide the various types of training programmes for the weavers in the respective handloom circles in Tamil nadu. In additions to it, weavers services centers (WSCs) are taking the responsibility of conducting the training for handloom weavers in all the district of Tamil nadu. In this connection, the Indian institute of Handloom technology (IIHT) Salem, The Ghandhi gram Rural University (GRI) Ghandhi gram and The National Institute of Fashion Technology (NIFT), Chennai are nodal agencies in this respect under integrated handloom development projects.

Statement of the Problem

The training to handloom weavers increases the productivity, co-operative team involvement and artisan’s commitment. It also redefines the weaving process with better quality. But it has certain drawbacks and issues such as loss of earning at the time of training period, additional cost for loom modernization, insufficient lecturing method, offering of the training to existing artisans not any other unemployed youth, Communication gap between the trainers and trainees. In this connection the particular factors like as lack of proper course materials and government authorities’ slowdown nature of work, the lack of contribution of hand loom weavers to the cost of training programme and formulation of training are also playing as the barriers to achieve the real goal of training programme. This problematic situation urges to undertake the research work entitled on “A Study on evaluation of handloom weavers’ training programmes provided in Thoppampatti block of Dindigul district of Tamil Nadu.

Objective of the Study

1. To study the demographical and occupational conditions of sample handloom weavers in Thoppampatti block of Dindigul district of Tamil Nadu.
2. To evaluate the nature and pattern of handloom weavers training programmes offered in Thoppampatti block of Dindigul district of Tamil Nadu.

3. To assess the benefits and improvement of training programmes offered to sample handloom weavers in Thoppampatti block of Dindigul district of Tamil Nadu.
4. To evaluate the perceptions of sample handloom weavers on training programmes offered in Thoppampatti block of Dindigul district.
5. To suggest the implementable recommendation to improve the quality and impact of handloom weavers training offered in Tamil nadu.

Research Methodology

It is a descriptive cum analytical study. Both the primary data and secondary data were collected. The survey method has been adapted to collect the primary data. The Annual reports of WCSs, WSCs, the policy note of Handloom and Textiles Government of Tamil Nadu, Annual reports of Textile Department, Government of India and other Records of WSCs were used as a secondary data. In this connection, the 50 handloom artisans weaving in the Thoppampatti block of Dindigul district were selected as sample respondents for this study through simple random technique by using lottery method in Chennai city. The well structured questionnaire was used to collect the data from the primary source. The collected data has been properly coded, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted by using statistical tools such as simple percentage, average, mean and “ T” test.

Demographic and Occupational Conditions of sample Handloom weavers

The majority of handloom weavers in Thoppampatti block of Dindigul District are jointly together and carrying their weaving activities through weavers co-operative societies named as Thiruvalluver Handloom Weavers Industrial co-operative societies ltd. Narikkalpatti, Kolumakudan WCS and Sri Sowdeashwariamman WCS , Shatnan chettivalasu . The Major varieties of production in this area are kora Silk Sarees and Pure Silk Sarees. Their average production per day is in the range from 2.5 meters to 5 meters. There are working in 20 to 25 days per month by an average. The majority of age group of sample weavers has belonged to the range from 31 to 45 years. Their earning per month spreads from Rupees 6001 to 12000 by an average. The Majority of weaving households have one or two handlooms per family by an average. (Table no. 1)

Nature and Pattern of Training programmes offered to Handloom weavers

The weaving training programmes has been provided to sample handloom weavers in Thoppampatti block at WCS s for the period of 45 days by the WSCs Narikalapatti . It is funded by the directorate of handloom and textiles, Government of Tamil Nadu. In addition to it, Dyeing (Tie and Dyeing) Training is provided for the period of one week to this sample weavers. Nearly Rupees 210 per day has been given to trainees as stipend during the training period to meet the travelling expenses and other conveyances. (Table -2)

Table -1 Demographic and Occupational Conditions of sample Handloom weavers in Thoppampatti block of Dindigul district of Tamil Nadu

Sl.no	Profile	No's of the sample Respondents	Percentage
I	Age		
	18 years to 30 years	12	24
	31 years to 45 years	25	50
	46 years to 60 years	10	20
	Above 60 years	03	06
	Total	50	100

II	Family Status		
	Joint family	18	36
	Nuclear family	28	56
	Single	04	08
	Total	50	100
III	Income Level per month		
	Below Rs. 6000 per month	07	14
	Rs.6001—12000	27	54
	Rs. 12001-20000	09	18
	Above 20 000	07	14
	Total	50	100
IV	No’s of Handloom		
	1 loom	28	56
	2 looms	22	44
	3 looms	00	00
	Total	50	100
V	Variety of Hand loom product weaving		
	Kora skill saree	34	72
	Cotton Saree	01	02
	Skill Saree	15	30
	Total	50	100
VI	Production attached with		
	WCSs	28	56
	MWs	22	44
	Total	50	100

Source: Compiled from primary data

Table -2 Nature and Pattern of Training programmes offered to sample Handloom weavers in Thoppampatti block of Dindigul district of Tamil Nadu

Sl.no	Profile	No’s of the sample Respondents	Percentage
I	Agency of Training programme		
	Handloom Training Center	02	04
	Weavers Training Center	39	78
	National Institute of Fashion Technology	03	06
	Indian Institute of Handloom Technology	06	12
	Total	50	100
II	Nature of Training		
	Weaving	39	78
	Dyeing	06	12
	Pre loom activities	05	10
	Total	50	100

III	Type of Training		
	In house Training	00	00
	In Training Center	05	10
	WCSSs	45	90
	Total	50	100
IV	Duration of Training period		
	One week	03	06
	8 days to 15 days	06	12
	16 days to 30 days	02	04
	Above 30 Days	39	78
	Total	50	100

Source: Compiled from primary data

Evaluation of the Handloom weavers' Training Programme

The evaluation of the present handloom weavers training system has been done through the assessing the gender wise perception of handloom weavers with the respect of impacts of training programme in their weaving and dyeing activities. For this purpose, The data obtained from the gender wise perception of handloom weavers with the respect impact of Training programme were fitted with 't' test to find out the association of the profile variable with the process of training system. The both male and female weavers has perceived highly the impact training programme as Reducing drudgery, Reducing wastage in weaving, Dyeing methods and Value addition of Cloth. (Table; 3)

Table 3 The evaluation of Handloom weavers Training system

Sl. No	Impact of Handloom weavers Training system	Male N=25		Female N=25		"t" Value	Level of Significance
		Mean \bar{X}	Std. Deviation 'S'	Mean \bar{X}	Std. Deviation 'S'		
1	Reducing drudgery	3.7356	1.005	3.9074	0.917	-1.04	0.300
2	Reducing wastage in weaving	3.6092	0.671	3.7963	0.655	-1.63	0.105
3	Increasing productivity	3.3448	1.180	3.7037	1.176	-1.96*	0.057
4	Value addition of Cloth	3.3103	0.919	3.3519	0.756	-0.07	0.945
5	Product diversification	2.7241	1.428	2.7407	1.362	-0.07	0.945
6	Improvement in the quality of cloth	3.2989	0.954	3.2037	0.959	0.57	0.567
7	Knowledge of new technology	3.4138	0.815	3.2407	0.910	1.14	0.256
8	Operational knowable on new kind of Equipment and accessories'	2.5517	1.139	2.3519	1.152	1.01	0.317
9	Dyeing methods	3.7366	1.105	3.8073	0.907	-1.14	0.299
10	Quality	3.5082	0.661	3.5961	0.605	-1.53	0.099
11	Dyeing fastness	3.2248	1.190	3.9037	1.076	-1.86*	0.049
12	Colour combination	2.7231	1.418	2.8407	1.382	-0.08	0.935

Source: Computed from respondents schedule * Significant at 5 percent level

It was noticed that the following impact of Training programmes such as performance management such as, Increasing productivity, and Dyeing fastness “ were statistically significant at 5 percent level, since the ‘t’ values were greater than the tabled ‘t’ value.

Suggestions and Conclusion

The government of Tamil Nadu should includes the local issues and challenges in framing the training programme. The Training for Marketing practice, Human Resource Development and costing practices should be provided. The trends of loom and weavers are in diminishing one from time to time. So The training programmes should be offered to fresh unemployed rural youth for their entrances into handloom filed.

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